

VAMANA AND VIRECHANA VYAPAT: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF CLASSICAL AYURVEDIC LITERATURE

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Article Received on 04 June 2026,

Article Revised on 24 June 2026,

Article Published on 01 July 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21033112>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Kamal Kishor Joshi^{*1}, Dr. Ruchi Gupta², Dr. Ketan Mahajan³, Dr. Shivani Mahajan⁴, Dr. Atul Sharma⁵, Dr. Ayushi Kasyap⁶. (2026). Vamana And Virechana Vyapat: A Systematic Review Of Classical Ayurvedic Literature. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(7), 431–467.

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ABSTRACT

Vamana (therapeutic emesis) and *Virechana* (therapeutic purgation) are cornerstones of *Ayurvedic Shodhana* therapy, designed to eliminate deep-seated vitiated *Doshas* and restore biological equilibrium. The clinical success of these bio-cleansing procedures is fundamentally dependent on the *Chikitsa Chatushpada* (the four pillars of treatment), consisting of the physician, the drug, the attendant, and the patient. Any deficiency in these pillars or errors in pre-operative preparation, such as inadequate *Snehana* (oleation) and *Svedana* (fomentation), can precipitate ‘*Vyapat*’ or complications. While *Charaka Samhita* details ten such complications, *Sushruta Samhita* identifies fifteen, *Astanga Hridaya & Samgraha* identifies twelve, primarily categorized into *Ayoga* (insufficient cleansing), *Atiyoga* (excessive cleansing), and *Mithyayoga* (faulty administration). Clinical manifestations range from *Adhmana* (abdominal distension) and *Hridgraha* (cardiac stiffness) to life-threatening *Jivadan*

(life-blood discharge). diagnostic differentiation of *Jivadan* involves classical animal-feeding and cloth-washing tests. Modern clinical research correlates these complications with acute electrolyte imbalances, particularly sodium and potassium depletion, and transient cardiovascular fluctuations. Management strategies involve specific hemostatic measures, specialized enemas like *Piccha Basti*, and adherence to *Purva Karma* (pre-operative) and

Pashchata Karma (post-operative) protocols remains the gold standard for preventing these complications and ensuring the safety of *Panchakarma* in contemporary practice. This article provides a thorough clinical investigation into the etiology, symptomatic profile, and classical management of *Vamana* and *Virechana Vyapat*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Vamana, Virechana, Vyapat, Shodhana Chikitsa.*

INTRODUCTION

In the *Ayurvedic* therapeutic framework, *Shodhana Chikitsa* (purification therapy) is prioritized for its unique ability to eradicate diseases from their root, thereby preventing the possibility of recurrence. Unlike *Shamana* (palliative) therapy, which aims to pacify or suppress *Doshas* within the body, *Shodhana* focuses on the total expulsion of excessively vitiated *Doshas* through the nearest natural physiological route.^[1] *Vamana* is specifically indicated for *Kapha*- predominant disorders via the oral route, while *Virechana* is the treatment of choice for *Pitta*- disorders via the anal route.^[2] While doshas subdued by fasting or digestive medicines may flare up again, those eliminated through *Shodhana* are eradicated at the root.^[3]

The clinical efficacy and safety of these bio-cleansing procedures rest upon the proficiency of the *Chikitsa Chatushpada*- the physician, medicine, attendant, and patient. A *Vyapat* (complication) occurs when this systemic balance is compromised, often due to inadequate pre-operative preparation or procedural errors. Any deficiency in these four limbs leads to clinical complications.^[4] For instance, performing *Shodhana* on a person who has not undergone proper *Snehana* and *Svedana* is comparable to trying to bend a dry stick, which results in internal tissue damage rather than successful cleansing.^[5] Furthermore, a physician must accurately assess the patient's *Kostha* and *Agni*; failing to do so may lead to the administration of *Tikshna* (sharp) drugs to a sensitive patient, resulting in traumatic hemorrhage or excessive fluid loss.

While *Charaka* identifies ten major *Vyapat*, *Sushruta* expands this diagnostic framework to fifteen types, specifically detailing directional anomalies like *Vamana-Adhogati* (downward movement of emetics) and *Virechana-Urdhvagati* (upwards movement of purgatives).^[6] Contemporary clinical studies have further correlated these classical complications with measurable physiological parameters. For instance, observations indicate that during *Vamana*, a volunteer's systolic blood pressure can transiently rise to between 100 and 170

mmHg. The diastolic BP during *Vamana* ranged from 70 to 100 mmHg and pulse rate during the *Vamana* procedure ranged 65 to 106/min.^[7] Furthermore, investigations into *Virechana* reveal statistically significant reductions in serum potassium (average 0.043 mmol/L) and sodium (1.80 mmol/L), which directly correlate with the classical symptoms of *Angagraha* (muscle cramps) and *Bala-Kshaya* (profound weakness).^[8] Understanding these complications through both classical scriptures and modern parameters is essential for evidence-based practice in modern healthcare environments.

Table No. 1: Classification of Vyapat According to Different Acharya.

<i>CHARAKA SAMHITA</i>	<i>SUSHRUTA SAMHITA</i>	<i>ASTANGA HRIDAYA & SAMGRAHA</i>
1. <i>Adhmana</i>	1. <i>Vamanasyadhogati Urdhwam Virechanasya</i>	1. <i>Pratikula gati</i>
2. <i>Parikartika</i>	2. <i>Savasheshoushadhatvam</i>	2. <i>Paka</i>
3. <i>Parisrava</i>	3. <i>Jeernaushadhatvam</i>	3. <i>Grathitvatva</i>
4. <i>Hridgraha</i>	4. <i>Heena Doshaapahritatva</i>	4. <i>Gaurava</i>
5. <i>Gatragraha</i>	5. <i>Vatashoola</i>	5. <i>Doshautklesa</i>
6. <i>Jeevadana</i>	6. <i>Ayoga</i>	6. <i>Adhmana</i>
7. <i>Vibhramsha</i>	7. <i>Atiyoga</i>	7. <i>Parikartika</i>
8. <i>Sthambha</i>	8. <i>Jeevadana</i>	8. <i>Parisrava</i>
9. <i>Upadrava</i>	9. <i>Adhmana</i>	9. <i>Pravahika</i>
10. <i>Klama</i>	10. <i>Parikartika</i>	10. <i>Hridgraha</i>
	11. <i>Parisrava</i>	11. <i>Gatragraha</i>
	12. <i>Pravahika</i>	12. <i>Sadhatusravana</i>
	13. <i>Hridayopasaranam</i>	
	14. <i>Vibandha</i>	
	15. <i>Angagraha</i>	

Vyapat according to Acharya Charaka

आध्मानं परिकर्तिश्च सावो हृद्गात्रयोर्ग्रहः।

जीवादानं सविभ्रंशः स्तम्भः सोपद्रवः क्लमः॥२९॥

अयोगादतियोगाच्च दशैता व्यापदो मताः।

प्रेष्यभैषज्यवैद्यानां वैगुण्यादातुरस्य च॥३०॥

1. *Adhmana Vyapat*^[9]

Nidana

Adhmana Vyapat usually develops when *Alpa Matra Aushadha* is given in a patient having *bahu Dosha Avastha*, *Ruksha Shareera*, *Agnimandya*, or *Udavarta* condition. In such

situations, the administered *Aushadha* becomes inadequate to eliminate the aggravated *Doshas* properly.

Samprapti

The given *Aushadha*, because of its *Guna*, causes *Dosha Utklesha*, but due to insufficient dose it cannot expel the *Doshas* from the *Shareera*. As a result, the aggravated *Doshas* create *Avarodhata* in *Srotas*, leading to accumulation of *Vata* and causing *Adhmana* mainly around the *Nabhi Pradesha*.

Lakshana

Patient may experience *Shoola* in *Prishtha*, *Parshva*, and *Shiras*. There may also be *Shwasa*, along with severe obstruction in passage of *Vit*, *Mutra*, and *Vata*. Abdominal distension and discomfort are commonly seen.

Chikitsa

Management includes *Abhyanga*, *Swedana*, *Varti*, *Niruha Basti*, *Anuvasana Basti*, and all forms of *Udavarta Hara Chikitsa* according to condition of the patient. The concept of *Adhmana Vyapat* is considered similar in both *Vamana* and *Virechana Karma*. In general terms, it can be understood as marked abdominal distension caused by improper elimination of aggravated *Doshas*.

2. *Parikartika Vyapat*^[10]

Nidana

Parikartika Vyapat occurs when *Tikshna Vairechaka Aushadha* is administered in a person having *Snigdha*, *Guru*, *Ama* or *Mridu Koshta* condition. It may also develop in individuals who are *Kshama*, *Shranta* or in *Alpabala Awastha*, where the body strength is reduced.

Samprapti

The *Tikshana Aushadha* acts rapidly and produces quick *Dosha Harana* along with elimination of *Ama*. Due to excessive sharp action, irritation and injury may occur in the lower gastrointestinal passage, resulting in *Parikartika*.

Lakshana

The patient may suffer from *Tivra Shoola* with *Picchila Rakta Srava*. Associated with cutting or burning type pain in the anal or rectal region, which is characteristic of *Parikartika*.

Chikitsa

- ❖ In same condition: use *Langhana, Pachana, Ruksha, Ushna* and *Laghu Ahara*.
- ❖ In *Kshama Purusha*: administer *Madhura Rasa Prayoga* along with all forms of *Brumhaniya Chikitsa*.
- ❖ If *Parikartika* persists even after *Ama Pachana*, advise *Kshara* and *Amla Rasa Yukta Laghu Aahara*.
- ❖ In excessive *Vata Lakshana*, give *Ghrita Snehapana* prepared with *Dadima Rasa*. This *Ghrita* may be combined with *Kasisa Bhasma, Yava Kshara* or *Saindhava Lavana*
- ❖ diet: use *Amla Rasa* along with *Dadima Twak Churna*.
- ❖ *Ushana Jala Pana*: can be given with *Devadaru* and *Tila Kalka*.
- ❖ *Ksheerapaka*: prepared from *Ashwatha, Udumbara, Plaksha, Kadamba Twak Churna*.
- ❖ *Sheetala Piccha Basti*: prepared using *Kashaya* and *Madhura Rasa Dravyas*.
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti*: with *Yashtimadhu Siddha Sneha*.

3. Parisrava Vyapat^[11]**Nidana**

Parisrava Vyapat develops when *Alpa Aushadha* is administered to a patient having *Bahu Dosha Awastha* and *Krura Kostha*. Because the *Aushadha* is insufficient, it fails to expel the aggravated doshas completely, resulting in this complication.

Samprapti

The administered medicine produces *Dosha Utklesha*, but due to inadequate potency or quantity, proper elimination does not occur. Instead, there is gradual and incomplete *Alpa Alpa Dosha Sravana* from the *Shareera*, leading to persistent morbidity.

Lakshana

Patient may present with *Kandu, Shopha, Kushta, Gouravata*, reduced *Agni*, decreased *Bala, Sthaimitya, Aruchi* and *Pandu*. These features indicate incomplete removal of *Doshas* with ongoing systemic disturbance.

Chikitsa

- ❖ In *Alpa Dosha Awastha*: adopt *Shamana Chikitsa*.
- ❖ In *Bahu Dosha Awastha*: perform *Snehana* and *Swedana*, followed by *Tikshna Virechana*.

- ❖ After *Samyaka Shodhana*: use *Churna*, *Asava*, and *Arishta Samskarita Aushadha Prayoga* for restoration and further management.

In *Bahu Dosha Awastha*, *Tikshna Virechana* is considered the main line of treatment. If there is *Kapha Srava* in *Mukha*, then *Tikshna Vamana* should be administered after proper *Snehana* and *Swedana Karma*. *Parisrava Vyapat* can be clinically understood as slow and incomplete discharge of aggravated *Doshas* due to inadequate purification therapy.

4. *Hridgraha Vyapat*^[12]

Nidana

Hridgraha Vyapat occurs when a patient suppresses the *Vega* generated during *Vamana/Virechana Karma*. Such suppression disturbs the normal movement of *Vata* and initiates pathology.

Samprapti

When the urge is forcefully controlled, *Vata* enters *Kupita Awastha* and becomes aggravated. The aggravated *Vata* then moves towards the *Hridaya* and causes severe constriction, pain, and functional disturbance known as *Hridgraha*.

Lakshana

The patient may develop *Hikka* (hiccups) *Kasa* (cough) *Parshwa Shoola* (pain in flank/lateral chest/side of thorax or upper abdomen) excessive *Lalasarava* (salivation), *Akshi Vibhramsha* (rolling or turtling of eyes), *Jihwa Khadita* (biting of tongue), *Nisangnya* (loss of consciousness) and *Dantan Kitikitayan* (clenching or grinding of teeth).

Chikitsa

- ❖ After proper assessment of *Dosha*, treatment should be selected accordingly.
 - In *Pittaja Murcha*: give *madhura aushadha yukta vamana*.
 - In *Kaphaja Murcha*: give *Katu Rasa Yukta Vamana Karma*.
- ❖ After *Vamana Karma*, the remaining *Doshas* should be managed with *Pachana Karma*. proper attention should be given to *Kaya Agni* and *Bala Vriddhi*.
- ❖ If excessive *Vamana* causes *Hridaya Shoola*, then *Vata Hara Chikitsa* should be adopted. Using *Snigdha*, *Amla*, and *Lavana Yukta Rasa*. Likewise, involvement of other *Doshas* should be assessed and managed with suitable treatment.

5. *Gatragraha Vyapat*^[13]

Nidana

Gatragraha Vyapat may develop in the following conditions:

- ❖ When a patient suppresses the natural *Vega* arising during *Vamana/Virechana karma*.
- ❖ when *Kapha* obstructs the *Vega*, preventing proper expulsion.
- ❖ Due to excessive *Shodhana*, where excessive purification weakens the body and aggravates *vata*.

Samprapati

Because of the above causes, *Vata* becomes aggravated and moves abnormally throughout the body. This disturbed *Vata* affects the *Gatra* (body parts and limbs), producing stiffness, pain, restricted movement, and neuromuscular discomfort resulting in *Anga Graha*.

Lakshana

The patient may experience: *Sthambha* (stiffness or rigidity of body parts), *Vepathu* (tremors or shaking), *Nistoda* (pricking type pain), *Saada* (loss of strength, fatigue, weakness), *Udweshтана* (twisting, cramping, or grinding pain), *Manthana Vat Shoola* (churning type severe pain), difficulty in movement and generalized body discomfort may also be present.

Chikitsa

- ❖ All *Vata Hara Chikitsa*

6. *Jeevadana Vyapat*^[14]

Nidana

Jeevadana Vyapat occurs when *Tikshana Aushadha* is administered in a patient having *Mridhu Koshta* or *Alpa Dosha Awastha*. In such conditions, the *Aushadha* acts excessively because the body does not require strong purification.

Samprapti

Due to the strong potency and high activity of the *Aushadha*, first *Dosha Hara* takes place, but later it may also cause *Rakta Hara*. This results in elimination of blood from the *Shareera*, sometimes in a churned or abnormal form, leading to serious depletion and threat to life.

Lakshan

The patient may developed: *Murcha* (fainting), *Trishna* (intense thirst), *Mada Lakshana* delirium/ altered sensorium).

Chikitsa

- ❖ After confirming the type of *Rakta Srava*, if *Shuddha Rakta* is being liminated, urgent treatment should be started.
- ❖ If patient develops *Murcha*, *Trishna*, *Mada Lakshana*, treatment should continue immediately to preserve life. Adopt all *Pitta Hara Chikitsa*. Example: *Sheetala Dravya Parisheka*, *Avagaha*, for *Sthambana*.
- ❖ Orally, fresh blood of liver deer, cow, buffalo has been classically mentioned for *Jeevana Dharana*, based on *Saamanya vishesha siddhanta*.
- ❖ If patient cannot drink fresh blood, then rakta basti chikitsa with fresh blood mixed with *Sukshma Churna* of *Darbha* (*Kusha*) is advised in classical texts.
- ❖ *Sheetala Basti*: *Ksheera Paka* prepared with *Shyama*, *Kashmarya*, *Badari*, *Durva*, *Usheera*, along with *Ghruta Manda* and *Rasanjana Churna*.
- ❖ *Sheetala Piccha Basti* may be given.
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti*: with *Ghruta Manda*.

7. Vibhramsha Vyapat^[15]

Vibhramsha Vyapat is explained in three different forms depending on the type of error or complication during *Vamana* and *Virechana*.

1. Gudabhramsha

Nidana: Atiyoga of *Virechana Karma*.

Samprapti: Excessive *Virechana* and straining weaken *Guda*, causing *Gudabhramsha* (rectal prolapse).

Lakshana: Rectum protrusion, pain, burning.

Chikitsa: *Kashaya Dravya Prakshalana*, Apply *Kalka*, reposition *Guda*, *Sthambhana Chikitsa*.

2. Sangya Vibhramsha

Nidana: Atiyoga of *Virechana*.

Samprapti: Excessive depletion may lead to *Murcha* (loss of consciousness).

Lakshana: Fainting, dizziness, weakness.

Chikitsa: Keep patient in peaceful environment, Reassure the patient, Soft pleasant music, Gentle communication and supportive care.

3. *Ayogajanya Vibhramsha*

Nidana: *Aushadha Ayoga* (inadequate action of medicine).

Samprapti: Only *Mala* or *Aushadha* comes out, while *Doshas* remain inside and get aggravated.

Lakshana: *Kandu*, heaviness, discomfort.

Chikitsa: Treat according to *Vyadhi*, use *Shamana* or proper *Shodhana*.

8. *Sthambha Vyapat*^[16]

Nidana

Occurs when *Sneha Vamana/Virechana Aushadha* is given to an already *Snigdha Rogi*.

Samprapti

Due to excessive unctuousness, *Dosha Avarana* occurs. The *Aushadha* becomes *Mridu* in action and fails to expel *Doshas* properly, causing retention of *Doshas* in their own site.

Lakshana

Vata Sangha, Guda Stambha, Shoola, Alpa-Alpa Dosha Ksharana.

Chikits

Perform *Langhana* and *Pachana* for *Dosha* digestion, followed by *Tikshna Basti* or *Tikshna Virechana*.

9. *Upadrava Vyapat*^[17]

Nidana

Occurs when *Ruksha Virechana Aushadha* is given to a patient having *Ruksha Shareera* and *Alpa Bala*.

Samprapti

Because of excessive *Rukshata*, *Vayu Kopana* takes place. Aggravated *Vata* spreads in the body and produces severe complications.

Lakshana

Stambha (severe stiffness), *Shoola* (intense pain), *Sarva Gatra Graha* (whole body rigidity), *Murcha* (fainting).

Chikitsa: *Snehana*, *Swedana*, All *Vata Hara Chikitsa*.

10. Klama Vyapat^[18]**Nidana**

Occurs when *Mridu Virya Aushadhi* is given to a *Snigdha* and *Mridu Koshta* patient.

Samprapti

The mild medicine fails to expel *Doshas* properly and causes vitiation of *Pitta* and *Kapha*, which obstruct the normal movement of *Vata*.

Lakshana

Tandra (Drowsiness), *Gaurava* (heaviness in body), *Klama* (mental fatigue *Daurbalyata* (General weakness), *Angasada* (bodyache).

Chikitsa

- ❖ *Vamana karma:* Immediate *Sadhyo Vamana* should be done.
- ❖ *Langhana* and *Pachana* for *Dosha* digestion.
- ❖ *Shodhana Karma:* Use *Tikshna Snigdha Aushadha*.

Vyapat according to Acharya Sushruta

तत्र वमनस्याधोगतिरूर्ध्वं विरेचनस्येति पृथक् । सामान्यमुभयोः- सावशेषौषधत्वं, जीर्णौषधत्वं, हीनदोषापहृतत्वं वातशूलम् अयोगः, अतियोगः, जीवादानम्, आध्मानं, परिकर्त्तिका, परित्रावः, प्रवाहिका, हृदयोपसरणं, विबन्ध अङ्गप्रग्रह इति ||3||

1. Vamana Aushadha Adhogamana Vyapat^[19]**Nidhana**

This complication occurs when *Vamana Dravya* is administered to a person suffering from *Bubhuksha* (hunger), *Tikshnagni*, *Mridu Koshta*, or *Durbala Avastha*. Due to similarity of *Guna*, the *Aushadha* fails to remain in *Amashaya* for the required duration and moves downward towards *Pakvashaya*.

Samprapti

The *Vamana Aushadha* does not stay in *Amashaya* long enough to produce proper *Dosha Utkleshana* and expulsion. Instead, it passes downward, leading to *Akrita Shodhana* and further aggravation of *Doshas*.

Lakshana

Ipsita Phala Anavapti (failure to achieve desired therapeutic effect), *Dosha Utklesha* (further aggravation/excitation of *Doshas*), Feeling of discomfort or incomplete cleansing.

Chikitsa

The patient should first undergo *Snehana Karma*. After proper *Snehana*, a more potent (*Tikshnatara*) *Vamana Dravya* should be administered to achieve proper *Shodhana*.

2. *Virechana Aushadha Urdhvagamana Vyapat*^[20]***Nidana***

This condition develops when *Virechana Dravya* is administered in *Ati Matra* (excessive dose), *Ahridya* (unpalatable medicine), in presence of *Ama*, *Ashuddha* in *Amashaya*, *Utklishta Shleshma*, or when undigested food (*Sashesha Anna*) is present in the stomach.

Samprapti

Because of *Kapha Prakopa*, *Ama*, or improper condition of *Amashaya*, the *Virechana Dravya* is not retained properly and instead moves upward, resulting in expulsion through the mouth rather than through the lower route. This leads to *Akrita Shodhana* and *Dosha Utklesha*.

Lakshana

Aushadha Chhardi (vomiting of the medicine), *Ipsita Phala Anavapti* (failure of desired purification), *Dosha Utklesha*, gastric discomfort.

Chikitsa

- ❖ If *Amashaya* is loaded with *Kapha (Ulbana Shleshma)*, first perform *Vamana Karma*.
- ❖ After cleansing *Amashaya*, administer *Tikshnatara Virechana Dravya*.
- ❖ If *Ama* is present, treatment should be done according to *Ama Chikitsa*.
- ❖ If the medicine is expelled due to *Ahridyata* or *Ati Matra*, a *Hridya* and *Matrayukta Virechana Dravya* should be given.

- ❖ If the *Aushadha* is expelled repeatedly, a third dose should not be administered instead, *Leha Yoga* prepared with *Madhu*, *Ghrita* and *Phanita* should be used for *Virechana*.

3. *Savashesha Aushadha Vyapat*^[21]

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered in *Alpa Matra* (insufficient dose). The *Aushadha* gets mixed with *Prakupita Doshas* and remains retained inside the body instead of producing proper *Dosha Nirharana*.

Samprapti

Due to inadequate quantity, the *Aushadha* fails to expel the aggravated *Doshas* completely. The retained *Aushadha* along with *Doshas* causes *Dosha Utklesha* and *Akrita Shodhana*.

Lakshana

Trishna (excessive thirst), *Parshva Shoola* (pain in flanks), *Chhardi* (vomiting), *Murchha* (fainting), *Parva Bheda* (joint pain), *Hallasa* (nausea), *Arati* (restlessness), *Udgara Avishuddhi* (impure eructation).

Chikitsa

The retained *Aushadha* should be expelled immediately by inducing *Vamana* with *Ushna Jala*. In *Balavan Rogi* with *Asamayak Virechana* and retained *Aushadha*, *Vamana Karma* should also be performed.

4. *Jirna Aushadha Vyapat*^[22]

Nidana

This condition occurs in a patient having *Krura Koshta* or *Tikshnagni*, when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered in *Alpa Matra* (small dose) or with *Manda Guna* (mild potency).

Samprapti

Due to strong *Agni* and resistant *Koshta*, the *Aushadha* gets digested like food before producing proper *Shodhana*. As a result, aggravated *Doshas* remain inside the body, causing *Akrita Shodhana*, *Dosha Utklesha*, and *Bala Hani*.

Lakshana

Ipsita Phala Anavapti (failure of desired purification), *Dosha Prakopa*, new disease manifestations (*Vyadhi Vibhrama*), *Bala Hani* (weakness /loss of strength).

Chikitsa

A stronger (*Tikshna*) and adequate dose of *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* should be administered for proper *Shodhana*.

5. Heena Aushadha Vyapat^[23]**Nidana**

This condition occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered without proper *Snehana* and *Swedana*, or when the *Aushadha* is of *Alpa Guna* (mild potency). As a result, only a small amount of *Doshas* gets expelled.

Samprapti

Due to incomplete *Dosha Nirharana*, residual *Doshas* remain inside the body and cause *Akrita Shodhana*, *Dosha Utklesha*, and aggravation of disease.

Lakshana**In Vamana Ayoga**

Gaurava (heaviness in the body), *Utklesha* (nausea/urge to vomit), *Hridaya Avishuddhi* (discomfort or heaviness in chest region), *Vyadhi Vriddhi* (aggravation of existing disease).

In Virechana Ayoga

Gudaparikartika (cutting pain in anal region), *Adhmana* (abdominal distension), *Shiro Gaurava* (heaviness in head), *Vata Anissarana* (difficulty in passage of flatus), *Vyadhi Vriddhi* (worsening of disease).

Chikitsa

- ❖ In *Vamana Ayoga*, *Tikshna Vamana aushadha* should be given.
- ❖ In *Virechana ayoga*, first perform *Snehana* and *Swedana*, then administer *Tikshna Virechana, Dravya* for proper *Shodhana*.

6. Vata shoola vyapat^[24]**Nidana**

This condition occurs when *Ruksha Aushadha* is administered without prior *Snehana* and *Swedana*, or when the patient does not follow *Brahmacharya* during *Shodhana Karma*. These factors aggravate *Vata Dosha*.

Samprapti

Aggravated *Vata* spreads throughout the body and affects different *Srotas* and *Marma Sthana*, producing severe *Vataja* in different regions.

Lakshana

Parshva Shoola (pain in flanks), *Prishtha Shoola* (back pain), *Shroni shoola* (pelvic pain), *Manya Shoola* (neck pain), *Marma Vedana* (pain in vital regions), *Bhrama* (giddiness), *Murcha* (fainting), *Sangya Nasha* (loss of consciousness).

Chikitsa

Perform *Abhyanga*, followed by *Dhanya Sweda*. After that, *Anuvasana Basti* with *Yashtimadhu Siddha Taila* should be administered.

7. *Ayoga Vyapat*^[25]***Nidana***

This condition occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is given without proper *Snehana* and *Swedana*, or when the *Aushadha* is given in *Alpa Matra* (insufficient dose) or has *Alpa Guna* (mild potency).

Samprapti

The *Aushadha* fails to expel *Doshas* through either the upper or lower route. Instead, it only causes *Dosha Utklesha* without proper elimination, leading to *Akrita Shodhana* and *Bala Kshaya*.

Lakshana

Adhmana (abdominal distension), *Hridaya Graha* (tightness/discomfort in chest region), *Trishna* (excessive thirst), *Murchha* (fainting), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Bala Kshaya* (weakness) If *Vamana Ayoga* persists, aggravated *Doshas* may spread throughout the body and cause; *Kandu* (itching), *Shwayathu* (swelling), *Kushtha* (skin disorders), *Pidaka* (eruptions), *Jwara* (fever), *Angamarda* (bodyache), *Nistoda* (pricking pain) If *Virechana Ayoga* occurs, it may cause: *Adho Nabhi Stabdha Purnodara* (distension below umbilicus), *Vata- Purisha Sanga* (retention of flatus and stool), *Shoola* (abdominal pain), *Kandu* and *Mandala* (itching and rashes).

Chikitsa

- ❖ In *Vamana Ayoga*, immediate *Vamana* should be induced using *Madanaphala* with *Lavana Jala*.
- ❖ In *Virechana Ayoga*, first perform *Asthapana Basti*, followed by *Snehana*, then administer *Tikshna Virechana Dravya*.
- ❖ *Ushna Jala* and local *Swedana* may be used to stimulate proper elimination.
- ❖ If *Doshas* are still not expelled, after about 10 days, proper *Snehana- Swedana* should be done and *Shodhana* repeated.

8. Atiyoga Vyapat^[26]**Nidana**

This condition occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered in *Ati Matra* (excessive dose) or with *Ati- Tikshna Guna* (very strong potency), especially in patients who have already undergone adequate *Snehana* and *Swedana* or in those with *Mridu Koshta*.

Samprapti

Due to excessive potency or dose, *Doshas* are expelled in excessive quantity, leading to *Ati Pravritti*, *Bala Kshaya*, and severe aggravation of *Vata Dosha*.

Lakshana**In Vamana Atiyoga**

Pitta Ati Pravritti (excessive expulsion of pitta), *Bala Hani* (loss of strength), *Vata Prakopa*.

In Virechana Atiyoga

Kapha Ati Pravritti followed by *Rakta Yukta Pravritti*, *Bala Hani*, *Vata Prakopa*.

Chikitsa**For Vamana Atiyoga**

- ❖ *Ghrita Abhyanga*.
- ❖ *Sheeta Jala Avagaha/Parisheka*.
- ❖ *Madhu- Sharkara Yukta Leha*.

For Virechana Atiyoga

- ❖ *Sheeta Jala Parisheka* or *Avagaha*.

- ❖ *Tandulodaka* with *Madhu*.
- ❖ *Piccha Basti*.
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti* with *Ksheera-Sarpis*.
- ❖ Light diet such as *Ksheera* or *Mamsa Rasa*.

9. Jivadana Vyapat

Nidana

Jivadana Vyapat develops due to *Atiyoga* of *Vamana* or *Virechana Karma*, especially when *Ati-Tikshna Aushadha* or *Ati Matra* of *Shodhana Dravya* is administered. Excessive expulsion causes severe *Pitta* and *Vata Prakopa*, leading to injury of *Antar Srotas*, *Dhatus*, and *Rakta Vaha Srotas*, resulting in discharge of *Jiva Shonita* (fresh vital blood).

1. Jivadana due to *Vamana Atiyoga*^[27]

Samprapti

Due to excessive *Vamana Vegas*, *Pitta* and *Vata* become highly aggravated. Continuous forceful vomiting injures the internal mucosa and blood vessels of *Amashaya-Urdhva Marga*, causing expulsion of blood through the mouth.

Lakshana

Rakta Chhardi / *Rakta Nishthivana* (vomiting or spitting of blood), *Jihva Nissarana* (protrusion of tongue), *Akshi Vyavritti* (abnormal movement/bulging of eyes), *Hanu Samhanana* (stiffness or locking of jaw), *Trishna* (excessive thirst), *Hikka* (hiccups), *Jwara* (fever), *Visanjnata* (fainting or altered consciousness).

Chikitsa

- ❖ Management should be done on the principles of *Rakta Stambhana* and *Pitta Shamana Chikitsa*.
- ❖ Give *Sheeta* and *Rakta-Stambhaka Dravyas*.
 - *Aja Rakta*, *Chandana*, *Ushira*, *Laja churna* with *Sharkara jala* may be used.
 - *Phala rasa* with *Madhu*, *Ghrita*, and *Sharkara* can be given.
 - *Ksheera* or *Jangala Mamsa Rasa* may be used for strength restoration.
- ❖ If associated complications occur:
 - *Jihva Nissarana* → apply *Trikatu-Lavana Churna* locally.
 - *Akshi Vyavritti* → *Ghrita Abhyanga* around eyes.
 - *Hanu Stambha* → *Vata-Kapha Hara Nasya* and *Swedana*.

2. *Jivadana due to Virechana Atiyoga*^[28]

Samprapti

Excessive *Virechana* causes continuous evacuation, severe *Vata-Pitta prakopa*, and damage to intestinal lining and *Rakta Vaha Srotas*, resulting in bleeding through *Guda Marga*.

Lakshana

The discharge usually progresses in stages:

Jala-Sadrisha Srava (watery discharge), *Mamsa Dhavana tulya srava* (discharge resembling meat washings), *Jiva Shonita Srava* (fresh red blood discharge).

Associated symptoms:

Guda Nissarana (rectal prolapse), *Vepathu* (tremors), *Bala Hani* (severe weakness), *Murchha* (fainting).

Chikitsa

Treatment follows *Ati Rakta Srava chikitsa*:

- ❖ *Piccha Basti*.
- ❖ *Ksheera-Ghrita Basti*.
- ❖ *Nyagrodhadi Kashaya Basti*.
- ❖ *Sheeta dravya* and *Rakta stambhaka yoga*.
- ❖ In *Guda Nissarana*, apply *Sneha*, followed by *Swedana* and reposition the prolapsed part.

10. *Adhmana Vyapat*^[29]

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered in a patient having *Bahu Dosha*, *Ruksha Sharira*, *Anila- Praya Koshta*, or *Sashesha Anna* in *Amashaya*, when the *Aushadha* used is *Asneha* (non- unctuous) or *Anushna* (not sufficiently hot in potency).

Samprapti

Due to improper preparation and unsuitable *Aushadha*, *Vata Dosha* becomes aggravated and causes obstruction in *Koshta*. This leads to retention of *Vata*, *Mutra* and *Purisha*, producing abdominal distension.

Lakshana

Vata-Mutra-Purisha Sanga (retention of flatus, urine, and stool), *Samunnaddha Udarata* (abdominal distension/bloating), *Parshva Bhanga* (pain in flanks), *Guda Basti Nistodana* (pricking pain in anal and bladder region), *Bhakta Aruchi* (loss of appetite).

Chikitsa

Treatment includes:

❖ *Upaswedana* (local fomentation), *Anaha Varti*, *Deepana Aushadha*, *Basti karma*.

11. Parikartika Vyapat^[30]**Nidana**

This condition occurs in patients who are *Kshama* (debilitated), *Mridu Koshta*, *Mandagni*, or *Ruksha prakriti*, when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* having *Ati- Tikshana*, *Ati- Ushna*, *atilaavana*, or *Ati-Ruksha Guna* is administered. These factors aggravate *Pitta* and *Vata Dosha*.

Samprapti

Due to aggravation of *Vata- Pitta*, irritation and injury occurs in *Guda*, *Basti*, *Nabhi* and *Medhra Pradesha*, leading to burning and cutting pain.

Lakshana

Guda Parikartana (cutting pain in anal region), *Nabhi Vedana* (pain around umbilicus), *Medhra Vedana* (pain in genital region), *Basti Vedana* (pain in bladder region), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Anila Sanga/ Vata Vishtambha* (retention of flatus), *Bhakta Aruchi* (loss of appetite).

Chikitsa

Treatment includes

- ❖ *Piccha basti* with *Yashtimadhu*, *Krishna Tila*, *Madhu* and *Ghritha*.
- ❖ *Sheeta jala parisheka*.
- ❖ Diet with *Ksheera* (milk).
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti* with *Ghritha Manda* or *Yashtimadhu Siddha Taila*.

12. *Parisrava Vyapat*^[31]

Nidana

This condition occurs in patients having *Krura Koshta* and *Bahu Dosha*, when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* of *Mridu Guna* (mild potency) is administered. The medicine causes *Dosha Utklesha* but fails to eliminate the *Doshas* completely.

Samprapti

Due to incomplete *Dosha Nirharana*, aggravated *Doshas* remain inside the body and try to come out repeatedly in small quantities, resulting in painful discharge of *Pitta* and *Kapha* through *Guda Marga*.

Lakshana

Daurbalya (weakness), *Udara Vishtambha* (abdominal rigidity/ distension), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Gatra Sadana* (body weakness/fatigue), painful passage of stools, repeated discharge of *Pitta* and *Kapha Yukta Mala*.

Chikitsa

Treatment includes

- ❖ *Asthapana Basti* with *Ajakarna*, *Dhava*, *Tinisha*, *Palasha*, and *Bala Kashaya* mixed with *Madhu*.
- ❖ After *Dosha Shamana*, perform *Snehana* then repeat proper *Shodhana Karma* with suitable *Aushadha*.

13. *Pravahika Vyapat*^[32]

Nidana

Pravahika Vyapat occurs when *Vamana* or *Virechana Aushadha* is administered after *Ati-rukshana* or *Ati-snehana*, or due to improper suppression (*Vegadharana*) of natural urges. these factors disturbed mainly *Vata*, *Kapha*, *Pitta Dosha*.

Samprapati

Due to *Dosha Prakopa*, especially *Vata* associated with *Kapha* and *Pitta*, the normal bowel movement gets disturbed, causing repeated expulsion of *Kapha Yukta Mala* with pain, burning, and urgency.

Lakshana

Frequent stool passage with urgency, *Shoola* (abdominal cramps/pain), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Vata Yukta Mala Pravritti* (passage of flatus with stool), *Picchila Mala* (slimy/mucous stool), stool may appear white, black, or blood mixed (*Shweta, Krishna, Rakta Yukta*), feeling of incomplete evacuation.

Chikitsa

❖ Treatment should be done on the principles of *Parisrava Chikitsa*.

14. Hridayopasarana Vyapat^[33]**Nidana**

This condition occurs when a patient suppresses the natural *Vegas* of *Vamana* or *Virechana* due to ignorance or fear. Due to suppression of these *Shodhana Vegas*, aggravated *Doshas* move abnormally towards *Hridaya*.

Samprapti

The obstructed *Doshas* move upwards or downwards and accumulate in *Hridaya* (*Pradhana Marma*). This causes severe pressure and pain in the cardiac region, along with disturbance of *Prana Vata* and loss of consciousness.

Lakshana

Hridaya Vedana (severe pain in cardiac region), *Danta Kitkitana* (grinding/cleansing of teeth), *Udgata Akshi* (upwards rolling of eyes), *Jihva Khadana* (tongue biting), *Murcha/Achetana* (fainting or unconsciousness).

Chikitsa

Treatment includes

- ❖ *Abhyanga* (oleation therapy).
- ❖ *Dhanya Sweda*.
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti* with *Yashtimadhu Siddha Taila*.
- ❖ *Tikshna Nasya* (*Shirovirechana*).
- ❖ *Vamana* with *Yashtimadhu Yukta Tandulodaka*.
- ❖ further *Basti Karma* according to *Dosha* predominance.

15. *Vibandha Vyapat*^[34]

Nidana

Vibandha Vyapat occurs when a patient, during *Vamana* or *Virechana Karma*, is exposed to *Sheeta Jala*, *Sheeta Vayu*, cold environment, or other improper regimens. These factors cause the mobilized *Doshas* to become thickened and obstruct the body channels.

Samprapti

The loosened *Doshas*, instead of getting expelled, become condensed and adhere to the *Srotas*, leading to obstruction in the passage of *Vata*, *Mutra*, and *Purisha*. This result in severe *Vata Prakopa* and blockage of natural excretory functions.

Lakshana

Vata-Mutra-Purisha Graha (retention of flatus, urine, and stool), *Atopa* (abdominal gurgling/distension), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Jwara* (fever), *Teevra Vedana* (severe pain).

Chikitsa

- ❖ Immediate *Vamana Karma* should be performed.
- ❖ Associated symptoms should be managed according to *Dosha* predominance.
- ❖ *Virechana* with *Adhobhaga Doshahara Dravyas* mixed with *Saindhava*, *Amla Dravya*, and *Gomutra*.
- ❖ *Asthapana* and *Anuvasana basti* according to *Dosha* condition.
- ❖ Proper *Pathya Ahara* based on *Dosha Avastha*.

Vyapat According to Astanga Hridaya & Samgraha

प्रतिकूला गतिः पाको ग्रथितत्वं सगौरवम्।

दोषोत्क्लेशो भृशाध्मानं परिकर्तः परित्रवः ॥४० ॥

प्रवाहिका हृद्ग्रहणं सर्वगात्रपरिग्रहः ।

सह धातुत्रवेणैता द्वादशोक्ताः ससाधनाः ।

व्यापदो विधिविभंशात्द्विविधेऽपि विरेचने । ॥४१ ॥

1. *Pratikula gati*

Vamana Aushadha Adhogamana Vyapat^[35]

Nidana

This complication occurs when *Vamana Dravya* is administered in patients with *Mirdu Koshta*, *Kshudha* (hunger), or *Alpa Kapha Avastha*. It may also occur when the medicine is *Ati- tikshna* (too strong), *Ati Sheeta* (too cold), *Alpa Matra* (insufficient dose), or when given in *Ajirna* and *Durbala* patients.

Samprapti

Due to improper patient selection or inappropriate *Aushadha*, the *Vamana Dravya* fails to stay in *Amashaya* and instead moves downward through *Adho Marga*. Because of this, proper *Kapha Nirharana* does not occur, leading to *Akrita Shodhana* and *Dosha Vriddhi*.

Lakshana

Vamana Aushadha passes through lower route.

Ipsita Phala Anavapti (desired therapeutic effect not achieved).

Dosha Vriddhi or *Mala Vriddhi*.

Feeling of incomplete purification.

Chikitsa

The patient should first undergo *Snehana Karma*. After proper *Snehana*, *Vamana Karma* should be repeated with suitable *Vamana Dravya*.

Virechana Aushadha Urdhavagamana Vyapat^[36]

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Virechana Dravya* is administered in patients having *Ajirna* or *Kapha Bahulya* (*Shleshma Vriddhi*). It may also occur when the medicine is *Ati- tikshna* (too strong), *Ati- ushna* (too hot), *Ati- lavana* (excessively salty), *Ahridya* (unpalatable), or given in *Ati Matra* (excessive quantity).

Samprapti

Due to *Ajirna*, *Kapha Avarana*, or unsuitable *Aushadha*, the *Virechana Dravya* fails to move through *Adho Marga* and instead gets expelled through *Urdhva Marga* as *Chhardi*. Because of this, proper *Dosha Nirharana* does not occur, resulting in *Akrita Shodhana* and *Dosha Utklesha*.

Lakshana

Aushadha Chhardi (vomiting of purgative medicine), *Akrita Shodhana* (incomplete purification), *Dosha Utklesha*, Failure of desired therapeutic effect.

Chikitsa

First perform *Snehana Karma*, then administer *Virechana* again with suitable *Virechana Dravya*.

2,3,4. Paka, Grathitvatva and Gaurava Vyapat³⁷¹

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Virechana Aushadha* is given without proper *Snehana* and *Swedana*, or when the medicine is *Purana* (old), *Ruksha* (dry), given in *Alpa Matra*. Gets digested by *Tikshnagni*, becomes ineffective due to *Sheeta Sevana*, or is administered in *Ama Avastha*. In such conditions, the medicine causes *Dosha Utklesha* but fails to eliminate them resulting in *Ayoga*.

Lakshana

Vibhramsha (discomfort/lack of interest), *Shwayathu* (swelling), *Hidhma* (hiccups), *Tamas darshana* (faintness/ seeing darkness), *Trishna* (thirst), *Pindikodveshtana* (calf muscle cramps), *Kandu* (itching), *Uru sada* (weakness in thighs), *Vivarnata* (discoloration).

Chikitsa

The patient should be treated as follows:

- ❖ Perform *Abhyanga* with *Taila* mixed with *Lavana*.
- ❖ Give *Swedana* by *Prastara Sweda* and *Sankara Sweda*.
- ❖ Administer *Niruha Basti*.
- ❖ Give food with *jangala Mamsa Rasa*.
- ❖ Follow with *Anuvasana Basti* using *Madanaphala*, *Pippali* and *Daruhaldi Siddha Taila*.
- ❖ Again perform *Snehana* with *Vatahara Sneha*.
- ❖ Finally, administer *Tikshna Virechana Dravya* for proper *Shodhana*.

5.6. *Doshautklesa and Adhamana Vyapat*^[38]

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Virechana Aushadha* is given in *Alpa Matra* to patients having *Bahu Dosha*, *Ruksha Sharira*, *Mandagni* or *Udavarta*. Due to insufficient potency, the *Aushadha* causes *Dosha Utklesha* but fails to eliminate them properly.

Samprapti

The aggravated *Doshas* obstruct the normal *margas* and mainly vitiate *Vata Dosha*. This leads to obstruction in *Koshta* and causes distension around *Nabhi Pradesha* along with pain and retention of natural urges.

Lakshana

Nabhi Adhmana (distension around umbilicus), *Prishtha Shoola* (back pain), *Parshva Shoola* (flank pain), *Shiro Ruja* (headache), *Shwasa* (difficulty in breathing), *Vit- mutra- Vata Sanga* (obstruction of stool, urine, and flatus).

Chikitsa

Treatment includes

- ❖ *Abhyanga*, *Swedana*, *Varti Prayoga*, *Niruha basti*, *Anuvasana Basti*, all *Udavarta Hara chikitsa* should be adopted.
- ❖ Additionally, *Yavagu* prepared with *Panchamoola*, *Yavakshara*, *Vacha*, *Bhutika*, and *Saindhava* is beneficial in relieving *Shoola*, *Vibandha*, and *Adhmana*.

7. *Parkartika Vyapat*^[39]

Nidana

Parikartika occurs when *Tikshna* or strong *Shodhana Aushadha* is administered in patients who are *Kshama* (emaciated), *Alpa Bala* (weak), *Mridu Koshta*, *Mandagni*, *Ruksha*, *Asnigdha*, *Aswinna*, or in *Sama Avastha* (ama present). These factors aggravate *Vata* along with *Pitta*.

Samprapti

Due to administration of strong medicine in an unprepared body, *Vata-Pitta Dosha* become aggravated and affect *Nabhi, Basti, Guda*, and *Medhra Pradesha*, causing irritation, dryness, and pain in these regions.

Lakshana

Nabhi Vedana (pain around umbilicus), *Basti Vedana* (pain in bladder region), *Guda Parikartana* (cutting pain in anal region), *Medhra Vedana* (pain in genital region), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Anila Sanga* (obstruction of flatus), *Vishtambha* (abdominal obstruction/constipation).

Chikitsa

- ❖ *Piccha Basti* with *Krishna Tila, Madhuka*, and *Madhu* or *Ksheera* processed with *Ksheeri Vriksha*.
- ❖ *Sheeta Jala Parisheka* (cold water sprinkling/bath).
- ❖ Diet with *Ksheera* (milk).
- ❖ *Anuvasana Basti* with *Ghrita Manda* or *Yashtimadhu Siddha Taila*.
- ❖ The patient should take equal quantities of *Pippali, Dadima Chara, Hingu, Shunthi, Amlavetasa*, and *Saindhava Lavana* should be administered with *Madhu, Ghrita*, or *Ushna Jala*.

If Ama is present (Sama Avastha)

- ❖ *Langhana* and *Deepana* should be done.
- ❖ *Laghu, ruksha, ushna ahara- vihara* should be advised.

After Ama Pachana (Nirama Avastha)

- ❖ *Laghu, Kshara, Amla Ahara* can be given.

If Vata is predominant

- ❖ *Dadhi Sara* with *Dadima Twak* or *Dadima Rasa* with *Ghrita* or *Tila- Devadaru Kalka* with *Ushna Jala*.

8. Parisrava Vyapat^[40]

Nidana

This condition occurs in patients with *Krura Koshta* and *Bahu Dosha*, when *Shodhana Aushadha* is given in *Alpa Matra*, with *Alpa Guna*, or when the *Aushadha* is *Mridu* and *Snigdha*. Such medicine causes *Dosha Utklesha* but fails to expel them completely.

Samprapti

The aggravated *Doshas* remain inside the body and are eliminated only in small quantities repeatedly, mixed with *Pitta* and *Kapha*. Due to incomplete *Shodhana*, *Doshas* continue to irritate the *Koshta* and produce *Parisrava*.

Lakshana

Alpa-Alpa Pitta- Kapha Yukta Mala Pravritti, *Vishtambha* (abdominal obstruction/fullness), *Gaurava* (heaviness in body), *Shotha* (swelling/oedema), *Kandu* (itching), *Panduta* (pallor/discoloration), *Anga sada* (weakness/fatigue), *Gulma* (abdominal lump/distension), *Shoola* (abdominal pain).

Chikitsa

- ❖ *Asthapana Basti* with decoction of *Tinisha*, *Dhava*, *Ashvakarna*, *Palasha* and *Bala* mixed with *Madhu*.
- ❖ After *Parisrava* subsides, Perform *Mridu Snehana*.
- ❖ Then administer *Tikshna Shodhana* for complete *Dosha Nirharana*.
- ❖ After proper *Shuddhi*, give *Deepana- Pachana Aushadha* like *Churna*, *Asava*, and *Arishta* to restore *Agni*.
- ❖ The patient should take equal quantities of *Pippali*, *Dadima Chara*, *Hingu*, *Shunthi*, *Amlavetasa*, and *Saindhava Lavana* should be administered with *Madhu*, *Ghrita*, or *Ushna Jala*.

9. Pravahika^[41]

Nidana

This condition occurs when, after taking *Shodhana Aushadha*, the patient either forcibly initiates the *Vegas* early or suppresses the natural *Vegas*. This disturbs the normal elimination of *Doshas* and vitiates mainly *Vata* along with *Kapha* and *Pitta*.

Samprapti

Due to improper handling of *Shodhana Vegas*, *Doshas* become aggravated in *Pakvashaya* and cause repeated, painful, and incomplete evacuation. As a result, stool mixed with *Kapha* is passed with excessive straining.

Lakshana

Sadaha Mala Pravritti (stool with burning sensation), *Sashoola Mala Pravritti* (painful defecation), *Sapiccha Mala* (slimy/mucus mixed stool), Stool may be *Shweta*, *Krishna*, or *Rakta Yukta*, *Kapha Yukta Mala*.

Chikitsa

- ❖ Treatment should be done similar to *Parisrava Chikitsa*.
- ❖ *Asthapana Basti* with decoction of *Tinisha*, *Dhava*, *Ashvakarna*, *Palasha* and *Bala* mixed with *Madhu*.
- ❖ After *Parisrava* subsides, perform *Mridu Snehana*.
- ❖ Then administer *Tikshna Shodhana* for complete *Dosha Nirharana*.
- ❖ After proper *Shuddhi*, give *Deepana- Pachana Aushadha* like *Churna*, *Asava*, and *Arishta* to restore *Agni*.
- ❖ The patient should take equal quantities of *Pippali*, *Dadima Chara*, *Hingu*, *Shunthi*, *Amlavetasa*, and *Saindhava Lavana* should be administered with *Madhu*, *Ghrita*, or *Ushna Jala*.

10. Hridgraha^[42]

According to Ashtanga Hridaya

Nidana

This condition occurs due to suppression (*Nigraha*) of *Shodhana vegas* after administration of *Vamana* or *Virechana aushadha*. Suppression aggravates mainly *Maruta* along with other *doshas*.

Samprapti

The aggravated *doshas* move towards *Hridaya* and produce severe *Hridgraha* by affecting the cardiac region and *Prana Vata*.

Lakshana

Hridgraha (severe tightness/pain in cardiac region), *Hidhma* (hiccups), *Parshva Ruja* (flank pain), *Kasa* (cough), *Dainya* (weakness/distress), *Lala srava* (excessive salivation), *Akshi Vibhrama* (abnormal eye movements), *Jihva Khadana* (tongue biting), *Danta Katakatayana* (grinding of teeth), *Murchha / Nisanjnata* (unconsciousness).

Chikitsa

- ❖ The physician should not become confused and should immediately induce *Vamana*.
- ❖ In *Pitta dominant Murchha*, use *Madhura dravyas*.
- ❖ In *Kapha dominant condition*, use *Katu dravyas*.
- ❖ Remaining *Doshas* should be digested with *Pachana dravyas*.
- ❖ Gradually improve *Agni* and *Bala*.
- ❖ If *Hridaya Peeda* is caused by aggravated *Vata* after excessive vomiting, administer *Snigdha, Amla, and Lavana dravyas*.
- ❖ In *Pitta-Kapha* predominance, treatment should be done accordingly.

According to Ashtanga Samgraha

Nidana

This condition occurs due to suppression (*Nigraha*) of *Bheshajodgara, Chhardi*, and other vegas after administration of *Shodhana Aushadha*. Due to suppression, *Vata* and other *Doshas* become aggravated and move towards *Hridaya*.

Samprapti

The aggravated *Doshas* reach *Hridaya* and affect the *Pradhana Marma*, producing severe *Hridgraha* and intense pain.

Lakshana

Severe *Hridaya Vedana, Moha* (confusion/unconsciousness), *Hidhma* (hiccups), *Kasa* (cough), *Lala srava* (excessive salivation), *Parshva Shoola* (flank pain), *Vepathu* (tremors) *Nashta Samjna* (loss of consciousness), *Danta Katakatayana* (grinding of teeth), *Udvritta Akshi* (upward rolling of eyes), *Jihva Khadana* (tongue biting).

Chikitsa

- ❖ Perform *Abhyanga* followed by *Dhanya Sweda* immediately.
- ❖ Administer *Tikshna Avapeeda Nasya*.

- ❖ Induce *Vamana* with *Yashtimadhu yukta Tandulodaka*.
- ❖ In *Kapha* predominance, use *Katu dravyas*.
- ❖ Remaining *Doshas* should be managed with *Pachana dravyas*.
- ❖ *Basti karma* should be administered according to *Dosha* predominance.

11. *Gatragraha*^[43]

According to *Ashtanga Hridaya*

Nidana

This condition occurs due to suppression (*Nigraha*) of *Shodhana Vegas* after administration of *Aushadha*, or due to obstruction of *Vata* by aggravated *Kapha*. It may also occur in an excessively purified (*Ati Vishuddha*) patient.

Samprapti

Obstructed or aggravated *Vata Dosha* spreads throughout the body and affects different body parts, leading to neuromuscular and painful symptoms.

Lakshana

Stambha (stiffness), *Vepathu* (tremors), *Nistoda* (pricking pain), *Sada* (weakness/fatigue), *Udveshtana* (twisting or spasmodic pain), *Arti* (severe discomfort), *Bhedana* (splitting type pain).

Chikitsa

- ❖ All *Vatahara Chikitsa* should be adopted, especially:
- ❖ *Snehana*, *Swedana*, other therapies pacifying *Vata Dosha*.

According to *Ashtanga Samgraha*

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Ruksha Virechana Aushadha* is administered in excessive dose to patients who are *Asnigdha*, *Aswinna*, *Abrahmachari*, *Vegadhari*, *Mridu Koshta*, or *Sukumara*. Such improper administration causes severe aggravation of *Vata Dosha*.

Samprapti

Excessive purgation leads to depletion of body unctuousness and aggravation of *Vata*. The aggravated *Vata* spreads throughout the body causing stiffness, pain, and neuromuscular disturbances.

Lakshana

Sarvanga Pragraha (stiffness of whole body), *Parshva Shoola* (flank pain), *Prishtha Shoola* (back pain), *Shroni Vedana* (pelvic pain), *Manya Vedana* (neck pain), *Marma Shoola* (pain in vital regions), *Murchha* (fainting), *Bhrama* (giddiness), *Kampa* (tremors), *Stambha* (rigidity), *Nistoda* (pricking pain), *Bheda* (splitting pain), *Udveshtana* (twisting pain/spasm), *Sangya Nasha* (loss of consciousness).

Chikitsa

- ❖ Perform *Abhyanga*.
- ❖ Give *Dhanya Sweda*.
- ❖ Administer *Anuvasana Basti* with *Yashtimadhu Siddha Taila*.
- ❖ Give *Vatahara Ahara* and *Pana*.

12. Sadhatusravana^[44]

According to *Ashtanga Hridaya*

Nidana

This condition occurs when *Ati- Tikshna Bhesaja* is administered to a patient who is *Kshudharta* or has *Mridu Koshta*. The strong *Aushadha* rapidly expels *Pitta* and *Kapha* and also causes excessive loss of body fluids and *Dhatu*s.

Samprapti

Due to excessive action of the *Aushadha*, not only *Doshas* but also *Dhatu Drava Bhaga* gets eliminated, leading to *Atiyoga Lakshanas* and depletion of strength.

Lakshana

- ❖ Excessive *Virechana/ Vamana*
- ❖ *Dhatu Kshaya*.
- ❖ Features of *Atiyoga* due to excessive elimination.

Chikitsa

- ❖ Remaining *Aushadha* should be counteracted with *Madhura Dravyas*.
- ❖ In *Ati Vamana*, administer *Mridu Virechana*.

- ❖ In *Ati Virechana*, administer *Mridu Vamana*.
- ❖ Perform *Sheeta Parisheka*, *Avagaha* and other *Sheeta* therapies.
- ❖ Give *Anjana*, *Chandana*, *Ushira*, *Aja Rakta*, and *Sharkara Jala*.
- ❖ *Mantha* prepared with *Laja Churna* is highly beneficial in *Atiyoga*.

According to *Ashtanga Samgraha*

Nidana

The condition occurs when *Tikshna Virechana Aushadha* is administered to patients who are *Snigdha*, *Swinna*, *Ati Mridu Koshta*, or *Kshudhita*. The *Aushadha* excessively expels *Malas* and also causes liquefaction and elimination of *Dhatus*.

Samprapti

Due to excessive action of *Virechana Dravya*, not only *Doshas* but also *Dhatu Drava Bhaga* gets eliminated, leading to severe depletion and *Atiyoga Lakshanas*.

Lakshana

- ❖ Excessive *Virechana*.
- ❖ *Dhatu Kshaya*.
- ❖ Features of *Atiyoga and Rakta- Pitta* may develop.

Chikitsa

- ❖ Perform *Abhyanga* with *Shatadhauta Ghrita*.
- ❖ Use *Kashaya*, *Madhura*, and *Sheeta* therapies like *Pradeha*, *Parisheka*, and *Avagaha*.
- ❖ Give *Leha* prepared with *Sharkara* and *Madhu*.
- ❖ Administer *Laja* and *Saktu* with *Chandana*, *Anjana*, *Ushira*, *Chhaga Asruka* and *Sheeta Jala*.
- ❖ Give *Piccha Basti*.
- ❖ Use *Ksheera* and *Ghrita* processed with *Madhura Varga Dravyas*.
- ❖ *Ghrita Manda Anuvasana* should be administered.
- ❖ Follow *Rakta-Pitta Chikitsa* siddhanta if required.

DISCUSSION

Vamana and *Virechana* are among the most extensively practiced *Shodhana* procedures in *Panchakarma* and are considered superior therapeutic modalities for the elimination of vitiated *Doshas*. The present review demonstrates that the concept of *Vyapat* is comprehensively elaborated in the *Brihatrayi*, reflecting the profound understanding of procedural safety and risk management in classical *Ayurveda*. Although *Charaka*, *Sushruta*, and *Vagbhata* differ in the number and nomenclature of *Vyapats* described, all authorities consistently emphasize that inappropriate administration of *Shodhana* procedures results in predictable pathological consequences.

A comparative analysis reveals that *Ayoga*, *Atiyoga*, and *Mithyayoga* constitute the fundamental pathogenic basis of most *Vamana Virechana Vyapats*. Inadequate *Purva Karma*, improper assessment of *Kostha*, *Agni*, *Dosha Bala*, *Rogi Bala*, and inappropriate selection of *Shodhana Dravya* emerge as the major contributory factors. The repeated occurrence of conditions such as *Adhmana*, *Parikartika*, *Parisrava*, *Hridgraha* and *Gatragraha* across classical texts indicates their significant clinical relevance and universal applicability in *Panchakarma* practice.

An important observation of this review is the predominance of *Vata Dushti* in the *Samprapti* of most *Vyapats* irrespective of the initiating factor. Whether caused by *Vegadharana*, *Atiyoga*, *Ayoga*, or inappropriate administration of *Tikshna Dravyas*, the ultimate manifestation frequently involves *Vata Prakopa* and *Srotorodha*. This explains the repeated recommendation of *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Basti* and other *Vatahara* measures as primary therapeutic interventions.

Furthermore, the detailed descriptions of *Jeevadana* and *Sadhatusravana* illustrate the *Ayurvedic* understanding of excessive purification and *Dhatu kshaya*. These conditions underscore the necessity of maintaining a therapeutic balance between adequate *Dosha Nirharana* and preservation of *Dhatu* integrity. The preventive emphasis found throughout the classical literature highlights that successful *Panchakarma* depends not only on effective *Dosha* elimination but also on strict adherence to procedural principles. Therefore, comprehensive knowledge of *Vyapat* remains essential for enhancing the safety, standardization, and evidence based application of *Panchakarma* therapies in contemporary clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

The classical *Ayurvedic* literature provides a highly systematic and clinically relevant account of *Vamana- Virechana Vyapat*, encompassing their *Nidana*, *Samprapti*, *Lakshana*, and *Chikitsa*. The present review highlights that despite variations in classification among *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Astanga Hridaya*, and *Astanga Samgraha*, the fundamental principles governing the occurrence and management of *Vyapat* remain remarkably consistent. These principles collectively emphasize the importance of appropriate patient selection, meticulous *Purva Karma*, rational drug selection, individualized dosage, and proper execution of *Panchakarma* procedures.

The review further indicates that most complications arise from *Ayoga*, *Atiyoga*, or *Mithyayoga*, reflecting deviations from established *Shodhana Siddhanta*. The predominance of *Vata* involvement in the pathogenesis of many *Vyapats* and the frequent recommendation of *Vatahara* interventions demonstrate the central role of *Vata* in maintaining procedural equilibrium during *Shodhana* therapy.

Moreover severe conditions such as *Jeevadana* and *Sadhatusravana* underscore the potential consequences of excessive purification and highlight the necessity of preserving *Dhatu Bala* during therapeutic interventions.

From a contemporary perspective, the concept of *Vyapat* represents an advanced framework of procedural safety, complication recognition, and therapeutic correction within *Ayurveda*. Understanding these classical principles is essential not only for preventing adverse outcomes but also for ensuring the standardization and quality assurance of *Panchakarma* practice. Future clinical and translational research should focus on correlating classical *Vyapat* with objective clinical parameters to strengthen the scientific validation of *Panchakarma*. Such efforts may contribute significantly towards improving the global acceptance, safety profile, and evidence-based integration of *Ayurvedic Shodhana* therapies into modern healthcare systems.

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